

The Strategy of Power Exercise in Bay of Bengal: Perspective of U.S & China

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to experiment the power exercise strategy in Bay of Bengal of Sino-U.S. This study shows to fundamental technical issues of Sino-U.S rising influence in Bay of Bengal. It is one of the important zone in the present geopolitical situation. This study is the great way process emphasize on the several issues such as, minerals resource, energy, geopolitics and the economical perspective. This experimental analysis has formulated under the power exercise in Bay of Bengal and run into the transit issues way forward to conflicting interest in several countries. To be focus point of strong relationship under the littoral region which is all of the function can be running approach economic transition in several time U.S and China obtain own interest build up while creating the conflicting issues. In others way the hazards situation to establish in the littoral region and discussed this study apply the mixed method for instance qualitative and quantitative. This study also dispute that the significance of Bay of Bengal rise in the recent years coming soon consider. All of the hard power has included the main area and running to dynamics zones. All the powerful country always impose their own interest fulfil turn out the demandable issues observation. In order to various dimension brings about the political economy and the power of various sectors clarify into the geopolitics and financial factors

INTRODUCTION

The Bay of Bengal is the strategic place of power competition occurs frequently increase in world politics. Basically, several powerful state believed that their power exercise depend on bilateral collaboration. As a result, states has decided to build up dynamics relationship which their ocean trading competition raising new heights. In recent time various development states has engaged collaboration build up to powerful states which their interest fulfil in bilateral issues. The financial growth of India, china, U.S and others powerful states has raised their major power infliction to bay of Bengal and then various trading partnership all over the financial sector developed with ocean countries. The U.S and China has applied to dynamics approach in Bay of Bengal due to raised business partnership . All over the time production transition use to right path way in Bay of Bengal and the adoption to Power distribution approach which are easy approved to goods transition through several ocean corridor. This region is importance frequently raising the current world politics due to indo Pacific strategy of U.S-China. All and equal has tried to dominate this region hold up their own transition issues. To proactive decision of Bangladesh government has increased the same approach infliction to the powerful states. Recently, U.S and Chinese dominance has raised in Bay of Bengal due to their own regional interest

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Bay of Bengal is the location of northern last part of the Indian ocean. It has been the significance sea pathway and the extended from the Indian coastal line and up to Sri-Lanka. The world wide turn above the population has made protocol countries the area of Bay of Bengal with frequently 500 million population and the number of expected potential rating 30% in 2021. It has created to high frequency collaboration on the sea transport corridor among several states. The strategic position of south Asian financial bloc known to regional perspective underground the minerals resource in Bay of Bengal. In 2022 reported to south Asian oil import through the bay of Bengal path way and great way vast area managed almost 200 billion essential goods of Bangladesh. To be great way strategic function has prevented to trading vulnerability under the Myanmar, Singapore, Indonesia, India into global financial power such as, U.S & Chinese strategy. The Atlantic sea port protection served way the marine high prevention the two powerful interest state and the trading facilities of migration protocol into the littoral region all around the Bay of Bengal. In the great way period to 1600 from 1800s, the Bay of Bengal stand with an intensive of trading partnership by the financial reaction of U.S and China. In the sea port area served almost 35 million people overcome their economical communication among several states through use to Bay of Bengal financial protocol of the maritime issues transition. Recently it has raised to importance geopolitics region on bilateral partnership among powerful state under the world wide backdrop. This region is more multidimensional history and transition process in the global level over the past century. Bangladesh have to increased financial collaboration this region inspiring several countries due to the resource of minerals property. In the protection diversity under the development partnership has promoted to U.S

and Chinese regional strategy. This strategy also refer to the domestic bilateral relations raised in Bay of Bengal.

The Brief history of the Bay of Bengal

First of all, this region remembered that a meaningful sea port but the regional coastal area have seen frequently seasonal disaster which most influence on littoral people. In other words state that three countries sea port were promoted to several commercial partnership in Bay of Bengal like as, Myanmar, Bangladesh, India. The northern part of the water of Bay of Bengal have major sea port of the Indian sea port communication build up that included the potential financial partnership of east Asia and gradual process of economics market benefits in Europe into the oil business gulf and frequently development in Africa. This regional dispute was not be visible powerful states in the past decades. But the last quarter of the years, this regional conflict have increased on the indo-pacific strategy of U.S-China. In ancient period , this regional backdrop was created the among sub continent countries and coastal zone in south China sea. The freedom of speech, ideas, various goods through Bay of Bengal which was promoted to littoral regional civilization. In 19th century, the several decades among the powerful states were raising trading partnership after the war period in Britain. In the great way dispute have access to British circulation and trading systemization of the coastal zone in Bay of Bengal. To be most of the littoral areas has known to as the indo Pacific region. In the 19th century was visible administration and political collaboration of several states on territorial areas of the British Raj. This Raj joined to Myanmar and expansion into the peninsula of Malaysia. In the maritime areas in major centre point Bay of Bengal coastal zone from Singapore to cyclone talk to advanced under the financial and political hegemony of British Raj. The geopolitical competition of various way integration of the littoral zone under the financial globalisation between U.S & China .

METHODOLOGY

The systematic investigation have conduct by the use of secondary data. Firstly I have selected to the reliable keywords and introduced to research question. I have also find out data resource in united states and Chinese definite database. In the meantime rational searching has to topics related review papers and technical reports are deeply reviewed. After the review process, only logical research materials has selected which use of better outcome. Finally I have postpone several error data tools which do not match with my research purpose. Some of the research question is given below:

- 1) What does cause of presence U.S & China in Bay of Bengal?
- 2) What are the instrument of reach into the Bay of Bengal?
- 3) What does the significance of littoral regional states?
- 4) How does transit contribution in Bay of Bengal?
- 5) How does applicable strategy in littoral regional history?

Data Collection Approach:

I have first collected data from books, journal, and English version printed news. I have also exact data find out from U.S state department database and Chinese foreign affairs. In addition to included several data source such as, Al-Jazeera, the CNN, Voice of America, The Guardian, Reuters and the Forbes. In another way to postpone error data from several critics media sources. I have apply several checking approach on all data resource which research collaboration to exact data use this study and remove to error data.

Cause of Raising Significance in the Bay of Bengal:

Economics Factors: The Bay of Bengal is the important role play in financial prosperity all over the global perspective. The sustainable food production help to the economic partnership through the sea port transition procedure. In order to the total amount goods have sold into the import-export systemization to be economical factors in Bay of Bengal. In 2021-22 period of U.S and China has to 10.5 million(t) goods export to south Asian region and almost creative entirely marine economic facilities more than 60% product dealing with Bangladesh through Bay of Bengal. Another neighbour country such as India the total own sea area turned out the main trading partnership circumstances in 38.9 billion USD amount of product export to several sea port oriented countries and economical agreement in the Bay of Bengal.

Factor of politics: The Bay of Bengal is the most important strategic area in current geopolitics perspective. It has several number of resource and financial transit pathway and the starting play a political dynamics in the area. Each of the countries their own interest serve and extended borders security, sustainable diplomacy promoted to this vital region. It has raised several countries territorial protection under the dispute agreement through the mainstream facilities pathway to the nation temporary regional dynamics. To be great way process into the own resource of Bangladesh always secret values of development countries under the prevent divergence of geopolitical interest serve into the U.S-China. In order to several country is frequently raise into the maritime trade procedure and under the gradual process of meantime circulation variety of distribution diplomatic protocol in the Bay of Bengal.

Factors of Energy Resource: To present time have to find out the vast number of energy reservation in Bay of Bengal. In order to deep prospect extended under the gas sector and another report to petroleum corporation state that this region is the high level petroleum resource which approval the various foreign company contract and systematic zone vocal point under the energy availability. The maritime economic zone has circulation thinking approach the unprecedented facilities of U.S and China. The ocean resource regarding main point task the U.S and China frequently dominance this area due to their protection aggressive economic interest serve to the development countries in Bay of Bengal. As a result, energy resource hub have to increase frequently significance zone in developed countries on the Bay of Bengal.

Factor of Connectivity: The Bay of Bengal refer to the another importance factor of world connectivity build up. It has importance point of indo Pacific region between U.S-Chinese power struggle . To be communication protocol in

Bay of Bengal under the gradual process of continuous act for protection linked into the India, Sri-Lanka and Bangladesh. It has raising connectivity purpose initiative and drastically growing concern alternative approach build up. The U.S-China has great way development protocol of littoral regional countries such as Chinese BRI project focus on Bay of Bengal regional country which visible development connection build up. In another several investment protocol has made significance zone under the U.S partnership of complexity connection in south Asia. The regional and sub regional connectivity have increased transportation systemization over the U.S and China through the Bay of Bengal. The Presence in Bay of Bengal of China:

The Bay of Bengal is the great way Chinese interest place frequently searching zone of the Malacca straits. The Indian scholar believe that several path way depressed and raising to Chinese arrivals in the Bay of Bengal in systematic purpose services. But various research organisation state that the goals of several targets of China such as economic and diplomatic partnership. This region on the Chinese plan to included the relationship under developed powerful U.S province to global financial by the strong route through the Bay of Bengal. In addition to see that find out the Chinese visions of alternative several path way. The main point of Malacca are well contribution on the world trading and oil business categories. It is small part of the sea path way between the Pacific area and Indian sea port. Then to the alternative sea route use Chinese visionaries protocol over the vital resource point of sentiment. In order to decrease dependency on Malacca polarisation pathway and linked build up with Myanmar. It is located the eastern china to sea port build up on the Myanmar region in Bay of Bengal. The relationship of the two states have to unite gas pipeline which beginning of the island on the coastal port of Myanmar and stops of Chinese regional sea port. In time of continuous same procedure is the china Myanmar oil pipeline. In this current time of Myanmar political challenging period is running the Chinese greatest initiative of BRI project growing with the military authoritarian government of Myanmar. In order to the diplomatic potential 2021, February the Chinese infrastructure of Kya gas steam united the power plant program. In the several reports find out the Chinese project has promoted to sea port trading partnership average U.S \$180 million. In the another month the regional energy investment project have deal with the total U.S \$ 2.5 billion which access by the Myanmar authoritarian military government. In this way trying to India get the North eastern region such as Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, Naga Land, Meghalaya, and Tripura on the sea port of economic progressive way. Though Bangladesh has created the transit facilities to India, a enemy region on the Dhaka in expelled it. In order to the India and Myanmar have to bilateral collaboration with U.S \$484 million project relationship between Kolkata sea port with others sea port. In the MOU of the Development project of India on the RAKHINE state was total average U.S \$25 million of the over period since five years. To point out the strong process collaboration of the Indian connectivity of Bay of Bengal on sea port. The great way significance policy recommendations have to Indian several project deal on the South Asian and the Indian ocean fulfil the leadership capacity of China.

Military Rating: The Indian ocean various security prevention method was focus on arrival peoples liberation army ,Navy. In order to the head of the Navy state that sometimes five-eight Chinese navy units visible to Indian ocean which our soldiers very concerns this case. In addition to the Chinese navy ships have must crossing the Bay of Bengal route uses their interest. The Chinese Navy soldiers included the anti piracy operations and their protection Chinese flag raise on the sea port visit in the Bay of Bengal sea port. In this part the Indian Navy have their bilateral resource management. In addition to this region of the Bay of Bengal U.S Navy landing port station which use this protection base reaction on the several criteria provide to help coastal zone of humanitarian and disaster relief control over the protection base criteria.

Function of Chinese Submarine: The region of Bay of Bengal of the Chinese Submarine functional activities have turn out the worried situation of India and developed their Naval abilities, increasing defence protection cooperation and development of the bilateral alertness. In current few times, the Chinese government frequently raising on the under water Naval instrument of coastal oriented countries on going in Bay of Bengal. In order to recent report, the Bangladeshi submarine BNS has to proactive action under the construction procedure of U.S \$1.2 billion at the Cox's Bazar district. It has establish the various big capabilities of six submarine and eight progressive war ships. Some of the collaborative attractions on the Chinese Submarine protective solution under the Navy of Myanmar in Bay of Bengal. All and equal protection of the sea port security in Bay of Bengal under the meaningful dangerous possibilities was growing into the financial impacts and the territorial security protection way on the Bay of Bengal.

Interest of China in Bay of Bengal: Almost we have seen that the china India dominance struggle in the Bay of Bengal. The Indian strategy have to creative perspective under the facing of Chinese aggression. In the gradual process raise on the critical energy imports of the middle east to the Beijing. In order to most importance of the sea port of the east west part of the Bay of Bengal and another perspective protection of average cause of maritime space dominate on the Bay of Bengal littoral countries. China is the great way interest serve such as the narrow import sea route almost affected 80% import and this time the negative impact on country. As a result, China can be managed to strong arrival to ensure the energy provide easily and growth of submarine protection on the Bay of Bengal.

The Existing of US in Bay of Bengal:

To present time the great way process can be increased the regional interest of U.S and it acknowledge to diversity of domestic financial strength. The highly economical transition can be promoted to high rating goods and policy enduring. Some of the potential bilateral collaboration have to Bay of Bengal and vast resourcefulness coalition under the proactive sustainability important visions on the U.S ships and raising facilities with the Asian countries growing the transition of China. To be present Biden administration can be requirement to the Asia region of U.S strategy as Chinese visible discord with the great way strategy focus on raising contribution overall protection. The present strategy U.S

officially visions contract with Chinese bonding and spouse countries as a strategic relationship. In this proactive protection of the balancing targets raising scenario on the U.S spouse countries and attracting potential members in China. To be differentiate important circulation is that U.S could not equal arrival in the Bay of Bengal. U.S facilities can be continuously longer relationship with the South Asian nation. To be includes this disqualify most of the countries in BOB already protection strong bonding with India or China when systematically projection on the Bay of Bengal region. To be present U.S strategy can be crucial role play this dependency strategy function united of the national order to protection opposite states power. In another significance term the U.S Navy can be power struggle projection abilities under the Bay of Bengal water wide trading partnership. China can be almost build up the alternative power raising interest in the Bay of Bengal on the special concern to America which to be visible increasing role approach facilities of the regional cooperation. U.S have tried to neglected the some sub-region of present century due to many others hazards by the access to china and India which most of the main sea port power and financial power of protective region in the hegemonic competition. In others accountability of set into the Chinese extended power linked to south Asian align countries. In the creative western Pacific of conjugation on sea power of India which most of the time threatening to U.S Navy soldiers. In this region the long term financial interest was threatening to any opposite powerful states and discord the balance of power in Bay of Bengal. In order to active visions development can be collaborative of Chinese proactive facilities in the coastal region countries. In meantime, the economical power have key to protection under the another trading pathway countries turned about the sea port of BOB. The many others main point under the Malacca areas exactly free and secure provision fund of the spouse countries. The U.S existing velocity to the Bay of Bengal financial power can be struggle opposite reaction of China and India. The world economic forum state that the U.S interest to Bay of Bengal in economic sector, energy sector and the transit issues which several Asian aligns countries building in the bilateral relations. In others issues of U.S Navy train provide to littoral region South Asian Navy soldiers, particularly Bangladeshi Navy. In front of the obtain geopolitics visions manage to interest checking model apply to the regional spouse countries and opposition enemy countries productive signature mind contribution under the own U.S advantage. It can be included the strategically contribution and encouraging in Bay of Bengal regional countries on bilateral relations.

The Dispute of Regionalism:

At the new concept of Bay of Bengal has made great way transaction. It is strong visible protection of the emergence of geopolitical disputes entirely on the Bay of Bengal. To be verbose seeing that sea port financial actors rapidly development which creation to the dominance situation in this region. In the great way diverse in 20th century and find out Re-joining the powerful circumstances of world geopolitical system. To be proactive territorial hazards situation can be that the water wide south china sea. In addition to various measure on Dhaka that the coastal zone dispute between India and Bangladesh

changing to present introduced of Burma world wide arbitration. To be creating the right way environmental build up the regional security in the Bay of Bengal. The historical significance has connected the two powerful countries such as U.S and China. In addition to the eastern India and northern Myanmar can be several territorial coastal zone connected velocity of political misunderstanding and regional strategy. As the creative financial unite and melody of geopolitical sector between U.S and China on Bay of Bengal. To be included the second decades of 21st century on the more indo Pacific region of the important sea port. Meanwhile the ancient era of mutual understand to china and India has ruined. But present situation states that the Bay of Bengal is the significance part of the geopolitical engagement among the China, U.S and India. To be implementation on the several measures for regional infrastructure growth china, India and united states. Today's this are raising visible as competitive. Though the avoid of regional connection terms raising the power struggle of sea port, the collaboration of geopolitical over significance major power dispute to restricted this region. The financial globalisation has extended to the various decades of regionalism perspective over the powerful states mistrust with each others. The geopolitical and geo economic dispute have beginning the regional construction and joining term of the Asian perspective. The most significance infrastructure of new regionalism have trend to measures from U.S and China.

Systematic Struggle in the Bay of Bengal with additional provincial Actors:

This study describe the systematic visions of the main actors in the Bay of Bengal. It is collaboration joining the aim of IOR of the vast areas communication. In this definite rating the system of Bay of Bengal may be objectives of general IOR strategy. The Bay of Bengal have to geographical number of countries access to the main sea port lines, Almost theoretically Malacca point and the significance to credible out of impacts in the massive areas. The Several scholar states that the region of central international dispute due to the trading system on sea port. To be several cause various main actors of powerful states to overlapping on the interest of Bay of Bengal. In the Main protection sub-sections describing the cause of Raising struggle for power exercise in Bay of Bengal. To be bilateral geo-systemic and economic major cause of creation of power struggle this region such as maritime power, energy security and connectivity capabilities. In another projection of this region Demand and supply energy production has to build up raising into the economical challenge on the regional activities. In the foreign countries can be depend on the import- export which deliberate by the sea port orientation under the raising element of potential execution of huge figure in the Bay of Bengal. To be recent proactive situation have to motivated others spouse countries under the abilities of resource military base situation in Bay of Bengal.

Significance of Sri- Lanka:

China and Colombo describe their trading systemization collaboration on several issues. The great way U.S and India have to business partnerships in the South Asian block and India is the biggest business partners of Sri Lanka on world wide perspective. Additionally, Sri-Lanka can be great way reception under the mostly verify Indian cooperation in disaster infrastructure building. The two importance enhanced protection under the trading facilities with the

shareholders of China and India. To be creating bonding systemization under the largest pointing investment of the world wide bilateral protocol. China has talk about the provisional promoting project at the new Colombo sea port and four ports way among dimension.

Significance of Myanmar:

To be understand that the Myanmar government can be various project deal with termination under the potential regional context to be reliable resourceful market economy on the sea port. In recent time, Myanmar gradually raise into the Southeast Asia link up the important part of Bay of Bengal. In order to the vital role play under the Chinese economic system which we have visible largely competition on trading infrastructure such as the kala den project included the Kolkata sea port and another project development Indian connection is the improvement of the maritime road. In order to China and Myanmar has to systematic collaboration with oil trading pipeline and potential facilities depend on Chinese economics. The successful build up the pipeline with Myanmar may decrease Chinese dependency on the Malacca by 40%. U.S similarly try to the access on Bay of Bengal investment almost \$10.2 billion which development of trading but no room of the region for U.S business security due to Chinese high helping protocol. Additionally U.S and China can be build up strong military cooperation with the Myanmar. In recent time, Myanmar gets military product facilities from china and taken extra military training from Chinese Navy offers. So, this country try to balance of power with two countries such as U.S and China.

Significance of Bangladesh:

For China and U.S importance can be great way access into the managing systematic zone of trading sector. Economically, both countries the financial abrogated under estimate provided to flows of sea port business import- export in Bangladesh. China and U.S has provided to the trading line of massive infrastructure projects facilities. To be understand that arrival to competition in the regional expectation of balancing power struggle. In this term great way protective variations over the strategic velocity in U.S and China. The Chinese facilities to Bangladesh can advance in the different form of economic aid, military facilities and the infrastructure progressive in the strategically viable which is massive facilities in Bangladesh and Chinese systematic goal fill up. Like china, U.S has trying to ensure in the pathway on Bay of Bengal through Bangladesh. Politically and systematically, U.S has been raising impacts on the coastal nation and visible greatest interest in the regional activities. Washington advance system may be adoption due to the political economic cause and the fertility of environmental circulation making turned out vocation move into the alternative approach for the number of investment location for production oriented visions of the several project deal in the Bay of Bengal. To be initial great way systematic goal have to development on the infrastructure allotments visions under Dhaka-cox's Bazars. To be understand Bangladesh and U.S build up bilateral dialogue session in several times of emphasize under the diverse issues which both countries new projection velocity development of relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The perspective of Bay of Bengal region the U.S and Chinese power strategy emphasize on their several own interest. The U.S and China has political, military, financial dominance build up this region. All of the regional countries have known to frequently about the Chinese financial power exercise and Navy threats. The financial power exercise are several Chinese goals including to the lowest type of power strategy in Bay of Bengal. It is the little concerns and evidence that Bay of Bengal region in U.S Navy power exercise is counterweight to Chinese financial struggle. The Bay of Bengal regional states are the massive interest with the U.S but Chinese power strategy tools apply the against powerful actors. The U.S and Chinese security protocol has to this region under the preferable own interest serves to impose this regional countries. The Bay of Bengal is direct bilateral relationship into the coastal region could remain the viable effort. The U.S and China should do more coordinates with the Bay of Bengal regional countries try to build up bilateral relations on the energy, Connectivity, political and the diplomatic sector.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Bay of Bengal refer to the security structure calls over the bilateral collaboration on the coastal area. U.S and China would be included bilaterally this regional connectivity than the dynamics relations under the financial sector reaction. All of the power strategy exercise on the faster to execution major power struggle. To be more evidence that several state connection able to domination on the regional activities. The multi-lateral stood up has to emerge into the several factors under the creative functional approach exercise to the partnership regional power struggle. It may be several protection approach created on the dynamics powerful states between U.S and China. The perspective of geopolitics on the Bay of Bengal have to included the difference way through the next provisions. It will be depended upon the several significance nature of coastal regional countries which the extraordinary development of ocean transit system financial rating recorded by U.S and China.

Figure 1. Map of the Bay of Bengal.
[Source: World Atlas Maps]

Figure 2. -[Source: Wwww.Statista.Com]

Figure 3. Top Six Annual Net Oil Importers-2022[Source:Www.Statista.Com]

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of The Strategy of Power Exercise in Bay of Bengal in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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